

MUHANDISLIK

& IQTISODIYOT

№2

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

2026 fevral

Milliy nashrlar

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08.00.00 – Iqtisodiyot fanlar

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ISSN: 3060-463X

РЭУ.РФ
РОССИЙСКИЙ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЙ УНИВЕРСИТЕТ
ИМЕНИ Г.В. ПЛЕХАНОВА
ТАШКЕНТСКИЙ ФИЛИАЛ

muhandislik **& iqtisodiyot**

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
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2026-yil, fevral

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- 05.01.00 – Axborot texnologiyalari, boshqaruv va kompyuter grafikasi
- 05.01.01 – Muhandislik geometriyasi va kompyuter grafikasi. Audio va video texnologiyalari
- 05.01.02 – Tizimli tahlil, boshqaruv va axborotni qayta ishlash
- 05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
- 05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
- 05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
- 05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
- 05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
- 05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
- 05.02.00 – Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik
- 05.02.08 – Yer usti majmualari va uchish apparatlari
- 05.03.02 – Metrologiya va metrologiya ta'minoti
- 05.04.01 – Telekommunikatsiya va kompyuter tizimlari, telekommunikatsiya tarmoqlari va qurilmalari. Axborotlarni taqsimlash
- 05.05.03 – Yorug'lik texnikasi. Maxsus yoritish texnologiyasi
- 05.05.05 – Issiqlik texnikasining nazariy asoslari
- 05.05.06 – Qayta tiklanadigan energiya turlari asosidagi energiya qurilmalari
- 05.06.01 – To'qimachilik va yengil sanoat ishlab chiqarishlari materialshunosligi
- 05.08.03 – Temir yo'l transportini ishlatish
- 05.09.01 – Qurilish konstruksiyalari, bino va inshootlar
- 05.09.04 – Suv ta'minoti. Kanalizatsiya. Suv havzalarini muhofazalovchi qurilish tizimlari
- 10.00.06 – Qiyosiy adabiyotshunoslik, chog'ishtirma tilshunoslik va tarjimashunoslik
- 10.00.04 – Yevropa, Amerika va Avstraliya xalqlari tili va adabiyoti
- 08.00.01 – Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 – Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 – Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 – Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 – Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 – Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 – Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 – Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 – Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 – Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 – Marketing
- 08.00.12 – Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 – Menejment
- 08.00.14 – Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 – Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 – Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 – Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

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Rayosatining 2024-yil 28-avgustdagi 360/5-son qarori bilan "Dissertatsiyalar asosiy ilmiy natijalarini chop etishga tavsiya etilgan milliy ilmiy nashrlar ro'yxati"ga texnika va iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha "Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali ro'yxatga kiritilgan.

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MUNDARIJA

RIVOJLANGAN MAMLAKATLAR BANKLARIDA RISK-MENEJMENTNING TASHKILYI MODELLARI.....	26
Madaminov Bekzod Allayarovich	
“HUDUDGAZTA‘MINOT” AJ DA AMALGA OSHIRILGAN LOYIHALAR SAMARASI	32
Shukurillaev Jahongir Botir o‘g‘li	
HARBIY XIZMATCHI AYOLLARNING MAXSUS KIYIM SIFATIGA QO‘YILADIGAN DASTLABKI TALABLARNI SHAKLLANTIRISH	37
Abduraxmanova N.D., Mirtolipova N.X., Nasirullayeva G.S.	
СОВРЕМЕННОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ НЕСПЕЦИФИЧЕСКОГО ЯЗВЕННОГО КОЛИТА У ДЕТЕЙ	42
Закирова Бахора Исламовна, Каримов Достон Рустам угли	
ОЦЕНКА ВОЗДЕЙСТВИЯ ФИСКАЛЬНЫХ И КРЕДИТНЫХ ИНСТРУМЕНТОВ НА РЫНКИ ВЫСОКОЛИКВИДНОЙ ПРОДУКЦИИ И ЕСТЕСТВЕННЫХ МОНОПОЛИЙ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН.....	48
Бекзод Умматов	
ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ СИСТЕМ БУХГАЛТЕРСКОГО УЧЕТА В УСЛОВИЯХ ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИИ: СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ ЭКОНОМИКО-СТАТИСТИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА.....	55
Вахидов Азизжон Саиджонович	
SUG‘URTA FAOLIYATIDAGI MOLIVAVIY RISKLAR: BAHOLASH VA MINIMALLASHTIRISH STRATEGIYALARI	58
Xalikulova Shirin Utkir qizi	
“ANDIJONDONMAHSULOT” AJ MISOLIDA XARAJATLARNING STRATEGIK BOSHQARUV HISOBİ: AMALIY TAHLIL VA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH TAVSIYALARI	62
Xayitboyeva Laylo Oybekovna	
XORIJİY MAMLAKATLARNING NORASMIY IQTISODIYOT DARAJASINI PASAYTIRISHDAGI TAJRIBASI	66
Alimardonov G‘ayratjon Nuraliyevich	
XO‘JALIK YURITUVCHI SUBYEKTLARDA BARQARORLIK HISOBOTLARI AUDITINI SHAKLLANTIRISH	72
Xolikov Ravshan Anvar o‘g‘li	
PUL - KREDIT SIYOSATINING TRANSMISSION MEXANIZMINI RIVOJLANTIRISH	76
Obidova Zilola Ikromjon qizi	
HOMILADORLIK DAVRIDA AYOLLARDA UCHRAYDIGAN GESTOZLI KATARAL GINGIVITNI KOMPLEKS DAVOLASHNI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH	81
Nomurodova Farangiz Lazizovna	
AGRAR KORXONALARDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARNI JORIY ETISHDA INVESTITSIYA MEXANIZMLARINING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI VA RIVOJLANTIRISH YO‘NALISHLARI	87
Egamberdiyev Abdujabbor Xusanovich	
YOSHLAR TADBIRKORLIGI VA KICHIK BIZNES IQTISODIYOTINI TA‘MINLASHDA INFRATUZILMALARDAN FOYDALANISH IMKONIYATLARI	92
Mirzatov Baxtiyor Toxirovich	
KICHIK BIZNES SUBYEKTLARI FAOLIYATINI BAHOLASH METODOLOGIYASINING MAZMUNI VA TAMOIYILLARI	96
Mavrulov Ravshan Nematjonovich	

УПРАВЛЕНИЕ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫМИ КОММУНИКАЦИЯМИ В ПРОЕКТАХ	101
Носирова Гулираъно Абдулазиз кизи	
DAVLAT BUDJETI JARAYONIDA MONITORING VA MOLIVAVIY NAZORATNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI	107
Yax'yayeva Dilfuza Bagdatovna	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASIDA KICHIK KORXONALAR RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISH MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	111
Axmedov Sanjar Temur o'g'li	
RAQAMLI MOLIVA TEXNOLOGIYALARI EVOLYUTSIYASINING ISTIQBOLLI YO'NALISHLARI VA YUZAGA KELISHI MUMKIN BO'LGAN XATARLAR TAHLILI	117
Ko'chimov Jahongir Shuxrat o'g'li	
GAZ VA GAZ KONDENSATINI YIG'ISH VA TAYYORLASH TIZIMLARI UCHUN ZAMONAVIY LOYIHALASH USULLARI TAHLILI	123
Abdirazakov Akmal Ibragimovich Namozov Og'abek Maxmud o'g'li	
AGILE PROJECT MANAGEMENT IN THE DIGITAL ERA: STRATEGIES, FRAMEWORKS, AND BEST PRACTICES FOR SUCCESS	128
Utkirova Maftuna Murodjon qizi	
O'ZBEKISTON EKSPORTYOR KORXONALARINING YANGI BOZORLARGA CHIQUISHIDA FAOL MARKETING VOSITALARIDAN FOYDALANISH HOLATI VA MUAMMOLARI	134
Baqoyev Sunnatillo Burxon o'g'li	
TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATIGA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNI JORIY ETISHNING ILMIY-NAZARIY ASOSLARI	139
Salaydinov Shodiyor Nizom o'g'li	
TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATIDA INVESTITSION LOYIHALARNI BOSHQARISH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING TASHKILIY-IQTISODIY JIHATLARI	144
Qurbonov Jasurbek Pozilovich	
OPTIMIZATION OF ROADSIDE AUTO CAMPING SITES (REST AREAS) ON HIGHWAYS USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: INFRASTRUCTURE GAPS AND CORRIDOR-BASED EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	150
Akramov Akbarjon Akmal ugli	
QURILISH KORXONALARIDA INNOVATSION MARKETING YONDASHUVLARINING AHAMIYATI	156
Aminov Abbas Mo'minboy o'g'li	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASIDA AHOLI ISH BILAN BANDLIGI SAMARADORLIGINI IFODALOVCHI KO'RSATKICHLAR	160
Abdusaidov Akmal Abduvaliyevich	
MINTAQADA XUSUSIY TIBBIYOT MUASSASALARIDA MARKETING STRATEGIYASI	165
Yakubov Temur G'anibekovich	
AHOLI DEMOGRAFIK JARAYONLARINI IFODALOVCHI STATISTIK KO'RSATKICHLAR TIZIMI	169
Siroj Zarina Rustambekovna	
AXBOROT MAHSULOTLARI BIZNESINING YAIM VA BANDLIKKA TA'SIRI: EKONOMETRIK TAHLIL	176
Abdullayev Abdulla Fayzulla o'g'li	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA SOG'LIQNI SAQLASH TIZIMINI IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING KONSEPTUAL ASOSLARI	181
Ziyodullayev Qahramon	
ЭНЕРГОЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ: ПОЛЬЗА ДЛЯ ЭКОНОМИКИ И ЭКОЛОГИИ	185
Хамдамова Гавхар Абсаматовна	
O'ZBEKISTONDA EKSPORTNI RAG'BATLANTIRISHNING MOLIVAVIY VOSITALARI VA ULARNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING ASOSIY YO'NALISHLARI	191
Mamatov Baxodir Quldoshovich	

KO'P QIRRALI VALLARNING SHAKLLANTIRISH METODLARI VA USULLARINI TAHLIL QILISH	197
<i>Xasanov Bobirmirzo Maxmudali o'g'li, Valixonov Dostonbek Azim o'g'li, Alibekov Rasulbek Qanotbek o'g'li</i>	
MINTAQA SANOATINING TARKIBIY TRANSFORMATSIYASI VA UNNING IQTISODIY O'SISHGA TA'SIRINI EKONOMETRIK MODELLASHTIRISH	205
<i>Abdinazarov Xusan Shaymanovich</i>	
RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SHAROITIDA SUG'URTA BOZORINING RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISH	209
<i>Nomozova Qumri Isoyevna</i>	
XALQARO STANDARTLAR TALABLARI ASOSIDA AUDITORLIK TEKSHIRUVINI TASHKIL ETISHNING ILMIY-NAZARIY ASOSLARI	216
<i>Akromov Shohrux Shuhrat o'g'li</i>	
QASHQADARYO VILOYATIDA XIZMATLAR SOHASINING RIVOJLANISHNI TARTIBGA SOLISH TIZIMI	221
<i>Achilova Firuza Kurbanovna</i>	
BANK MENEJMENTIDA INKLYUZIV MOLIYALASHTIRISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI, TAMOYILLARI VA STRATEGIK AHAMIYATI	225
<i>Rajabov Oybek Panjievich</i>	
MINTAQADA OLIY TA'LIM TIZIMINING ISHSIZLIK DARAJASIGA TA'SIRINI EKONOMETRIK MODELLASHTIRISH	229
<i>Rustamov Jasurbek Ravshanbek o'g'li</i>	
MAISHIY XIZMATLAR SOHASIDA INNOVATSION KLASTER MODELINI JORIY ETISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI	235
<i>Normurodova Zebo Eshmaxmatovna</i>	
RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA INVESTITSIYA FAOLIYATINI BOSHQARISH	240
<i>Xatamov Nurbek Ochildiyevich, Sharifi Abdul Fatah</i>	
MOLIYAVIY REJALASHTIRISHNING AMALDAGI MUAMMOLARI VA ULARNI YECHIMI YUZASIDAN TAKLIFLAR	245
<i>Pardayev Jamshid Muzaffarovich</i>	
TIJORAT BANKLARI LIKVIDLIK RISKLARINI BAHOLASH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI	251
<i>Sulaymanov Samandarboy Adhambek o'g'li</i>	
O'ZBEKISTON TIJORAT BANKLARIDA RISKLARNI BOSHQARISH AMALIYOTINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	257
<i>Karimov Shohrux Boydulla o'g'li</i>	
"O'ZBEKISTON TEMIR YO'LLARI" AKSIYADORLIK JAMIYATINING HISOBOTLARINI XALQARO STANDARTLARGA TRANSFORMATSIYA QILISH	262
<i>Astanov Zafar Murodillayevich</i>	
QARAMA-QARSHI AYLANUVCHI IKKI ROTORLI SHAMOL TURBINASINING MATEMATIK MODEL	266
<i>Pirmatov Nurali Berdiyevich, Bekishev Allabergen Yergashevich, Saodullayev Abror Saypullayevich, Qurbonov Najmiddin Abduxamidovich</i>	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA KICHIK VA O'RTA BIZNESNI BARQAROR RIVOJLANTIRISHNING INSTITUTIONAL VA INVESTITSION MEXANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	272
<i>Norboev Sarvar Azodovich</i>	
O'ZBEKISTONDA TRANSPORT SOHASIDA FAOLIYAT YURITAYOTGAN TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARINING IQTISODIY AHAMIYATI	277
<i>Jaloliddinov Anvar Jaloliddin o'g'li</i>	
ANALYSIS OF UZBEKISTAN'S MAIN ECONOMIC INDICATORS AND GDP GROWTH	283
<i>B.Beknazarov</i>	

SOTISH JARAYONIDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA MARKETING TADQIQOTLARINING INTEGRATSIIYASI	288
Abduxalilova Laylo Tohtasinovna	
ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА В АУДИТЕ ФИНАНСОВОЙ ОТЧЕТНОСТИ: ГЛОБАЛЬНЫЙ И УЗБЕКСКИЙ КОНТЕКСТ	294
Мегноров Алмардон Абдирахмонович	
RISK MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES IN UNCERTAIN ECONOMIC ENVIRONMENTS: A GLOBAL COMPARATIVE STUDY	302
Nigmatova Malika	
OLIIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA MOLIIYAVIIY BARQARORLIKNI TA'MINLASHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	307
Hamrayev Maqsudjon Saidaxmadovich	
BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHNI TA'MINLASHDA AHOLI BANDLIGINI OSHIRISH MASALALARI	311
Mamajonova Gulbaxor Toxirjon qizi	
АВТОМАТИЗАЦИЯ АУДИТОРСКИХ ПРОЦЕДУР НА ОСНОВЕ ЦИФРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ И МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫХ СТАНДАРТОВ: ВЛИЯНИЕ НА КАЧЕСТВО АУДИТОРСКИХ ЗАКЛЮЧЕНИЙ	316
Киличева Ф.Б.	
MAISHIY TEXNIKA EKSPORTIDA YASHIL IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIKNI BAHOLASHNING NAZARIY-METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI	320
Kushmanova Mahbuba	
GAZ TA'MINOTIDA YO'QOTISHLARNI KAMAYTIRISHNING IQTISODIY ASOSLARI	324
Xamidov Xayriddin Faxritdinovich	
DAVLAT AKTIVLARINI XUSUSIYLASHTIRISHNING MINTAQA IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHIGA TA'SIRINI BAHOLASH (QASHQADARYO VILOYATI MISOLIDA).....	329
Sharapov Farrux Shomuratovich	
КРИТЕРИИ ОТБРАКОВКИ ЭКСТРУЗИОННЫХ АЛЮМИНИЕВЫХ ПРОФИЛЕЙ ГРУППЫ ALMGS1 ПО МАКРОСТРУКТУРНЫМ ПРИЗНАКАМ В ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕННЫХ УСЛОВИЯХ	333
Ибрахимов Фаррухжон Фарходович	
AKSIYADORLIK JAMIYATLARIDA DEBITORLIK QARZLARI VA FAKTORING OPERATSIYALARI HISOBINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	336
G'oziyeva Mokhira Rustamovna	
KULTIVATOR YUMSHATKICH PANJALARI O'TMASLANISH DARAJASINING ISH KO'RSATKICHLARIGA TA'SIRI	345
Quvondiqov Yoqub Tursunbaevich, Nuraliyev To'liqin Alimardanovich	
SANOAT KORXONALARINI BOSHQARISHDA INNOVATSION STRATEGIYANI RIVOJLANTIRISH BO'YICHA XORIJIY TAJRIBALAR	352
To'g'onov Ibroximxo'ja	
TMK KORXONASI SHAROITIDA R6AM5 MARKALI TEZKESAR PO'LATDAN TAYYORLANGAN PARMA UCHUN TERMIK ISHLOV BERISH REJIMI	358
Djalalova Sevara Toxtamuratovna	
РОЛЬ ЦИФРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В РАЗВИТИИ ИНКЛЮЗИВНОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ	362
Шоев Алим Халмуратович	
TRANSFORMATSIYA VA XUSUSIYLASHTIRISH OMILLARINING BANK SAMARADORLIGI KO'RSATKICHLARIGA TA'SIRI	367
Umirzoqova Aziza Olim qizi	
SANOAT KORXONALARIDA INNOVATSION BOSHQARUV SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH	372
Ismatov Raxmatilla Oltinovich	
RAQAMLI TO'LOV TIZIMLARI TADBIRKORLIK SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH OMILI SIFATIDA.....	376
Yoqubjonov Ibrohim G'olibjon o'g'li	

BANK TIZIMIDAGI AKTIVLARINING UNUMDORLIGINI OSHIRISH BO'YICHA STRATEGIK YONDASHUVLAR	379
Sadikov Q.M.	
СЦЕНАРНОЕ МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЕ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭНЕРГОЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ОТРАСЛЕЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА В УСЛОВИЯХ НЕОПРЕДЕЛЁННОСТИ И СТРУКТУРНЫХ ПРЕОБРАЗОВАНИЙ	383
Муслимова Ф.С., Хашимова Н.А.	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA TIBBIY XIZMATLARNI TAQDIM QILISHNING INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLARI	390
S.M. Raximova	
YANGI O'ZBEKISTONDA OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARI AXBOROT-RESURS MARKAZLARI FAOLIYATINI STRATEGIK BOSHQARISH MODELI	395
Qurbanova Muazzam Fazliddinova	
IQTISODIYOTNING TRANSFORMATSIYALASHUVI JARAYONIDA INVESTITSION KREDITLASHNING TAHLILI	399
Tuxsanov Eldor Dilmurod o'g'li	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA EKSPORTNI RAG'BATLANTIRISH MASALALARI	404
Abdug'aniyev Murodjon Shavkat o'g'li	
XO'JALIK YURITUVCHI SUBYEKTLARNING INNOVATSION FAOLIYATINI INVESTITSIYALAR YORDAMIDA QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASH	408
Baxriddinov Nodirbek Zamirdinovich	
FRANSUZ TILIDA FE'L SEMANTIKASINING KO'PMA'NOLILIK VA BIRMA'NOLILIK ASPEKTLARI	412
Jo'rayeva Malohat Muhammadovna, Bekmetova Munisa Karimbayevna	
QORAQALPOG'ISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA ASOSIY KAPITALGA KIRITILGAN INVESTISIYALARDA CHET-EL INVESTISIYASI VA KREDITLARINI ROLI	418
Sultanov Anvar Abdullaevich	
INSON QON TOMIRLARINING TARMOQLANISHINI L-SISTEMALAR ASOSIDA HOSIL QILISH ALGORITMNI ISHLAB CHIQUVISH	423
Boliyeva Dilrabo Nurbek qizi	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT LOYIHALARINI MOLIALASHTIRISHDA DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIK (DXSH)NING AHAMIYATI	429
Ergashev Axmadjon Maxmudjon o'g'li	
NAMANGAN VILOYATIDA TURIZM SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING STRATEGIK YO'NALISHLARI	434
Otaylor Usmonaliyev	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA VALYUTA ARBITRAJI VA UNING MOHIYATI	440
Yaxyayev Ziyodilla Lutfullayevich	
TIJORAT BANKLARI TOMONIDAN ALOQA SOHASINI MOLIALASHTIRISHNING NAZARIY JIHATLARI	443
Mirzaraximova Aziza Azimdjanovna	
DON VA UN MAHSULOTLARINI QAYTA ISHLASH KORXONALARIDA MARKETING FAOLIYATINI BOSHQARISH XUSUSIYATLARI	450
Boyjigitov Sanjarbek Komiljon o'g'li	
SURXONDARYO VILOYATIDA TUXUM ISHLAB CHIQUVISHNING JORIY HOLATI TAHLILI	454
Ismoilov Zuhridin Sayitqulovich	
ZAMONAVIY TURAR-JOY ME'MORCHILIGIDA MILLIYLIK VA AN'ANAVIYLIKNING O'RNI VA AHAMIYATI	459
Toshniyozov Otabek Hakimovich	
MARKAZIY QIZILQUM FOSFORIT RUDALARIDAN QIMMATBAHO KOMPONENTLARNI KOMPLEKS AJRATISH TEXNOLOGIYASI	464
Eshonqulov Uchqun Xudaynazar o'g'li, Ruzibayeva Dildora Akramovna, Xushvaqtova Dilshoda Shavkat qizi	

BANKLARDA CHAKANA KREDITLASH JARAYONLARINI RAQAMLASHTIRISH TARTIBI	470
<i>Axmedova Dilrabo Kurbondurdi qizi</i>	
TADBIRKORLIK VA KICHIK BIZNESNI QO‘LLAB-QUVVATLASHNING XALQARO MODELLARI HAMDA ULARNING AMALIY AHAMIYATI	476
<i>Nodirbek Shavkatovich Mirzaaxmedov</i>	
DAVLAT FUQAROLIK XIZMATIDA XOTIN-QIZLARNING BOSHQARUV KARYERASI: MOHIYATI, ZARURIYATI VA ILMIY-NAZARIY ASOSLARI	483
<i>Abduraxmonova Feruzabonu</i>	
ASOSIY KAPITALGA INVESTITSİYALARNI MOLIYALASHTIRISHNING RIVOJLANAYOTGAN MAMLAKATLAR TAJRIBALARI	489
<i>Xoshimov Sobir Murtazayevich</i>	
QURILISH MATERIALLARI ISHLAB CHIQARUVCHI KORXONALARDA MARKETING FAOLIYATINING TASHKILY TUZILMASINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH	495
<i>Uzakova Umida Ruziyevna</i>	
OLIY TA‘LIMNI MOLIYALASHTIRISH SAMARADORLIGI VA PROFESSOR-O‘QITUVCHI–TALABA NISBATI O‘RTASIDAGI IQTISODIY BOG‘LIQLIK.....	502
<i>Dusanov Salim Mamarasulovich</i>	
МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ОПЫТ ВНЕДРЕНИЯ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА В СИСТЕМЫ AML: АНАЛИЗ ПРАКТИК ВЕДУЩИХ БАНКОВ И СТРАН СНГ	507
<i>Рашидов Авазбек Рахимович</i>	
BOJXONA TIZIMINI RAQAMLASHTIRISHDAGI MAVJUD MUAMMOLAR TAHLILI	516
<i>Radjapova Latofat Sardorovna</i>	
DEFORMATSİYALANUVCHAN STANDART CHIZIQLI QATTIQ (STANDARD LINEAR SOLID MODEL, SLS) MODEL ISHLAB CHIQISH VA SONINI TAHLIL QILISH	523
<i>Ahmadov Ilhom Aktam o‘g‘li, Faxriddinova Rayhona Vahobjon qizi, Rustamova Ruxsora Kamtar qizi</i>	
ВЛИЯНИЕ КЕРАМИЧЕСКИХ КОМПОЗИЦИОННЫХ ПОКРЫТИЙ НА ТЕПЛОВУЮ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ КАМЕННОГО ТЕПЛОАККУМУЛЯТОРА В СОЛНЕЧНО-АССИСТИРОВАННЫХ БИОГАЗОВЫХ УСТАНОВКАХ	530
<i>Д.М. Жураханов</i>	
O‘ZBEKISTONDA ISLOMIY MOLIYA TIZIMINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING KELAJAKDAGI IMKONIYATLARI.....	537
<i>Akbarov Husniddinjon Mo‘ysin o‘g‘li</i>	
MAHALLIY BUDJETLARNI BOSHQARISHDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA OCHIQLIKNI KUCHAYTIRISH	544
<i>Xolmirzayev Ulug‘bek Abdulazizovich, Normatov Joxongir Murodillayevich</i>	
DON MAHSULOTLARI TARMOG‘IDA ISHLAB CHIQARISH QUVVATLARIDAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH MEXANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	548
<i>Aipova Iroda Ikramovna</i>	
BUXORO VILOYATI SANOATI ISHLAB CHIQARISHINING TARMOQ TARKIBI DINAMIKASI VA UNDAGI O‘ZGARISHLAR TAHLILI	554
<i>Toshov Mirzabek Hakimovich</i>	
TEMIR YO‘L TRANSPORTINING RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISH MEZONLARI	560
<i>Nurxo‘jayeva Xilola Hakimxo‘jayevna</i>	
СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В УПРАВЛЕНИИ УГОЛЬНОЙ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТЬЮ НА ОСНОВЕ УСТОЙЧИВОСТИ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКОГО КАПИТАЛА	568
<i>Teshaboyev To‘lqin Zakirovich, Muradov Botir Xayat</i>	
IQTISODIYOT TARMOQLARIDA SUV ISTE‘MOLINING BOSHQARUVINI RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING NAZARIY JIHATLARI	578
<i>Karimov Anvarjon Muqumjonovich, Turg‘unov Muhammadaziz Baxtiyorjon o‘g‘li</i>	
SUV RESURSLARINI BOSHQARISHDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA MOBIL ILOVALAR ASOSIDA SAMARADORLIKNI OSHIRISH MEXANIZMLARI	584
<i>Karimov Anvarjon Muqumjonovich, Uzakov Sirojiddin Djuraboyevich</i>	

SUN'IY INTELLEKT VA IQTISODIYOTNING O'ZARO ALOQADORLIGI	591
Sobirov Abdurasul Abdugafarovich	
IDENTIFICATION OF WEAVING STRUCTURES IN PILE FABRICS	596
Bahrom Baturovich Dautov, Bakhtiyor Yormakhmatovich Abduganiyev, Erkin Shamsiddinovich Rayxonov, Nazar Kilichov Bafoevich	

IDENTIFICATION OF WEAVING STRUCTURES IN PILE FABRICS

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Abstract. This article provides detailed information about the identification of pile fabric weaving processes, their characteristics, production technologies, and research methods. Pile fabrics are analyzed as one of the most complex types of textiles and are classified based on the arrangement of warp and weft threads. The equipment used in the research and the sequential steps of the testing process are described. The practical importance of pile fabric identification and the methodology of laboratory tests are also explored.

Keywords: pile fabrics, textile weaving, identification methodology, warp-weft threads, laboratory research, artificial fur, velvet, plush, velour, textile technology.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada tukli matolarning to'qilish identifikatsiyasi, ularning xususiyatlari, ishlab chiqarish texnologiyasi va tadqiqot metodlari haqida batafsil ma'lumot beriladi. Tukli matolar gazlamalar guruhining murakkab turlaridan biri sifatida o'rganilib, arqoq va tanda iplarning joylashuviga ko'ra ajratiladi. Tadqiqotda qo'llanilgan uskunalar va sinov jarayonining ketma-ketligi tavsiflangan. Tukli matolar identifikatsiyasining amaliyotdagi ahamiyati va laboratoriya sinovlarining metodologiyasi o'rganilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: tukli matolar, gazlama to'qilishi, identifikatsiya metodikasi, arqoq-tanda iplar, laboratoriya tadqiqoti, sun'iy mo'yna, barxat, plyush, velvet, tekstil texnologiyasi.

Аннотация. В данной статье подробно рассматривается идентификация тканых текстильных материалов с ворсом, их характеристики, технологии производства и методы исследования. Ворсовые ткани изучаются как одна из сложных групп текстильных материалов, различаемых по расположению нитей основы и утка. Описывается оборудование, используемое в исследовании, и последовательность проведения испытаний. Изучается практическая значимость идентификации ворсовых тканей и методология лабораторных испытаний.

Ключевые слова: ворсовые ткани, текстильное ткачество, методика идентификации, нити основы-утка, лабораторные исследования, искусственный мех, бархат, плюш, велюр, текстильные технологии.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the range of fabrics is extremely diverse and continues to expand due to advancements in modern science and technology. This process is driven by changing fashion trends and the human desire for aesthetic expression [1]. The expansion and diversity of fabric assortments require systematic study and categorization into specific groups. Examples include cotton fabrics, linen fabrics, pile fabrics, woolen fabrics, silk fabrics, blended fabrics made of chemical fibers, special and technical fabrics, and more. This study provides information about pile materials, their types, and unique characteristics [2].

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Pile fabrics are materials entirely or partially covered with pile. Depending on the type of fabric, the pile may be located across the entire surface or only in specific areas [3].

The pile length in such fabrics ranges from millimeters (or even smaller) to several centimeters. Modern types of pile fabrics include artificial fur, velvet, plush, velour, and others. Their price depends on the raw materials, application, production technology, and fabric type [4].

The manufacturing technology of pile fabrics determines their structure. Any type of raw material can be used: natural, artificial, synthetic, or mixed. According to state standards, fabrics can be made of cotton, silk, viscose, polyester, wool, and others [5].

The most common pile fabrics are traditional velvet (barxat), plush, velvet, and artificial fur. Traditional velvet (barkhat)– characterized by densely packed, almost vertically aligned pile about 2–3 mm long on the surface [6].

Plush – a heavy fabric with long, soft, slanted (sometimes patterned) pile, used for women’s and children’s coats, furniture, and curtains.

Artificial fur – distinguished by the length of its pile [7].

Velvet – features a pile layer on the surface in the form of strips or grooves [8].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

For pile fabric identification, the directions of warp and weft threads are determined, and the pile’s arrangement is analyzed to classify the fabric as warp-pile or weft-pile [9].

Tools used:

- “Prior” light microscope.
- Sharp scissors.
- Needle for sample preparation.
- Digital camera.

Sample collection. The sample was taken as a single piece that fully reflects the characteristics of the pile fabric. The sample was collected across the length and width of the fabric, including warp and weft threads, as well as the selvage.

The selvage refers to the reinforced edges of the fabric formed during the weaving process, which prevents the fabric threads from unraveling. Selvages are formed on both sides of the fabric and run along the entire length of the roll. For analysis, a pile fabric sample was taken with a length of no less than 20 cm and across the entire width of the fabric. The sample was cut according to the type of laboratory test to be conducted, ensuring its suitability for testing. Using sharp scissors, the sample was cut without any tearing, along its full width and the specified length. The sample must be in a condition suitable for research purposes.

Sequence of research. The prepared sample is separated from the weft threads along the selvage. During this process, attention is given to whether the pile is attached to the warp or weft threads.

Weft-pile fabrics. Weft-pile fabrics consist of three thread systems: one warp thread and two weft threads. The first weft forms the fabric in combination with the warp threads, while the second creates long loops, which, when cut, produce the pile surface.

All weft-pile fabrics have high-density weft threads and low linear density cotton fibers. Examples of such fabrics include traditional velvet, which features a pile coating along the weft direction, and semi-velvets with a uniform pile covering the entire surface (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Arch-pile thread

The prepared sample is separated along the warp threads. Attention is paid to whether the pile is attached to the warp threads or the weft threads (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Crosswise pile thread

Warp-pile fabrics. Warp-pile fabrics are formed using a system of five threads: three warp threads and two weft threads. Two warp threads and two weft threads create separate base fabrics, while the third pile-forming warp is cut with a blade, producing two pile fabrics with pile surfaces on the textile. Pile fabrics woven from natural silk or artificial threads include materials such as duchess satin, plush, and faux fur.

Analysis and results

If the pile in our sample separates along the weft threads, the sample is classified as a warp-pile fabric. This is because the pile is attached to the weft threads and woven parallel to the warp threads (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Warp-Pile Fabric

If the pile in our sample separates along the warp threads, the sample is classified as a weft-pile fabric. This is because the pile is attached to the warp threads and woven parallel to the weft threads (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Types of woven fabrics distinguished by the arrangement of yarns and weaving method

The range of pile fabrics today is very diverse, and with the development of modern technology and science, it continues to expand. Pile fabrics such as velvet, plush, velour, and faux fur vary depending on the raw materials and production technology. The production of such fabrics, their structure, and pile arrangement allow them to be classified as warp pile fabrics or weft pile fabrics.

In the study, the fabric type was analyzed under a microscope to observe the alignment of the pile with respect to warp and weft threads. According to the results, if the pile aligns with the warp thread, the fabric is classified as warp pile. If the pile aligns with the weft thread, the fabric is classified as weft pile.

The alignment of the pile with warp or weft threads plays a key role in the classification of pile fabrics in the Commodity Nomenclature of Foreign Economic Activity (HS), where codes 5801 33 and 5801 37 are assigned to such fabrics.

For example, if the warp yarns of the fabric consist of polyefir fibers and the weft yarns are made of cotton, the method of IR spectroscopy is used in practice to identify the separated yarns. In our practice, spectra in such cases were obtained using the Perkin Elmer Spectrum Two FTIR Spectrometer (Figure 5).

Figure 5. IR spectrum of cotton

Cotton IR spectrum (Infrared spectrum) analysis can be as follows: Infrared (IR) spectroscopy is widely used to determine the chemical composition and structure of cotton material. This method identifies the main functional groups in cotton and their vibrational spectral signals.

~3300-3500 cm^{-1} range - A broad and strong signal in this region indicates water (H_2O) or moisture in cotton. O-H peaks may also be present, as cotton consists of natural fibers with hygroscopic properties. ~2900-3000 cm^{-1} - This signal typically represents vibrations of CH_2 and CH_3 groups, related to organic fibers and carbon chains in cotton. ~1730-1650 cm^{-1} range (strong signal) - Vibrational signals of carbonyl ($\text{C}=\text{O}$) groups may be present in this region. However, since cotton is a natural fiber, carbonate or other substances are more likely to be present here rather than carbonyl groups. ~1600-1500 cm^{-1} (mixed signals) - May be related to aromatic or other conjugated groups. For cotton as the primary fiber, carbonate or other deformational vibrations may be present in this region. ~1200-1000 cm^{-1} range - Vibrations of O-H, C-O, and other oxidized groups are located in this region. May be related to polysaccharides and lignin in cotton.

Cotton's IR spectrum helps study its chemical composition and structural characteristics. Among the main spectral lines, vibrational signals of water, organic fibers, and polysaccharides are identified. Spectral data can be used to evaluate cotton quality, moisture content, and compositional components (Figure 6).

Figure 6. IR spectrum of polyester

Polyester IR spectrum analysis is as follows - the main lines and signals in the spectrum correspond to the chemical structure of polyester. IR spectroscopy is used to identify the main functional groups and bonds in polyester.

~2916-2917 cm^{-1} - Vibrations of CH_2 and CH_3 groups are present in this region. This indicates the presence of ethyl or methyl groups in polyester. ~1714 cm^{-1} - This signal represents vibration of the carbonyl ($\text{C}=\text{O}$) group. For polyesters, this is the most fundamental and strong signal, being their main characteristic. This signal is specific to the ester groups in polyesters. ~1455 cm^{-1} and ~1370-1380 cm^{-1} - Deformational vibrations of CH_2 and CH_3 groups may be present in these regions. ~1245-1248 cm^{-1} - This frequency corresponds to carbonate bonding or ethyl ester groups. Characteristic of ester bonds in polyesters. ~1084-1094 cm^{-1} - Vibrations of C-O and oxidized groups are present in this region, which is one of the main bonds in polyesters. ~720-730 cm^{-1} - Deformational vibrations of CH_2 groups may be present in this region.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The IR spectrum of polyester is distinguished by strong and broad spectral signals of the carbonyl ($\text{C}=\text{O}$) group, indicating its ester bonding. Vibrations of CH_2 and CH_3 groups are clearly visible in the spectrum. C-O bonds and deformational vibrations are identified in the spectrum. This spectrum provides information about the chemical structure and compositional components of polyester.

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muhandislik **& iqtisodiyot**

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir Alibekov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Abdurahmon Qurbonov

2026. № 2

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"Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali 26.06.2023-yildan
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi
Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan
№S-5669245 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №095310.

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